

Evaluating Common Bacterial Contaminants in Sesame Products: A Study of Tahini, Tahini-Halva and Shukri-Halva.

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Abstract

Sesame, an ancient crop cultivated for over 5,000 years, plays a significant role in various cuisines, particularly in the Mediterranean and Middle Eastern regions, where it is commonly used in foods such as tahini and halva. Given its widespread use, it is imperative to monitor potential bacterial contamination in sesame products. This study aimed to assess the prevalence of *Salmonella* spp, *Escherichia coli*, and *Bacillus cereus* in sesame-based products, including tahini, Shukri-halva, and tahini-halva, across different factories in Iran's Yazd province.

A total of 177 samples (59 samples each of tahini, Shukri-halva, and tahini-halva) were collected and subjected to bacterial isolation and identification using conventional bacteriological techniques. The results revealed that *Salmonella* spp. was detected in three samples (1.7%), while *E. coli* was present in 16 samples (9%), and *B. cereus* was isolated from 17 samples (9.6%) (p value ≤ 0.05).

These findings underscore the presence of potentially harmful bacterial species, particularly *E. coli* and *B. cereus*, in sesame products within the Yazd province of Iran, with *B. cereus* showing a higher prevalence. To safeguard public health and ensure the quality of sesame-based products, it is imperative for stakeholders involved in the production chain to receive comprehensive training on hygienic practices.

Keywords: Salmonella spp, Escherichia coli, Bacillus cereus, Sesame products, Halva.

1. Introduction

Sesame is one of the ancient crops cultivated and consumed in various countries for over 5 thousand years [1]. It is utilized to produce a variety of foods such as oil, tahini (sesame paste), and halva. Tahini is particularly popular in the Mediterranean and Middle Eastern regions, where it serves as a commonly consumed, ready-to-eat food [2]. To produce tahini, de hulled sesame seeds undergo processing and roasting without altering their natural composition. However, due to inadequate heating during the roasting process and the increased thermal resistance of bacteria on sesame seeds with low water activity (aw), some bacteria may survive the heating process [3, 4], or contamination might occur during milling or packaging [5]. Tahini is rich in fat, protein, and carbohydrates [6], as well as essential minerals like magnesium, phosphorous, potassium, and calcium [7].

Nonetheless, although tahini typically contains moisture levels of 1-2%, with a water activity ranging from 0.17 to 0.31, and a pH of approximately 5.9 [7, 8], its shelf life at room temperature is generally one year [9]. Tahini is utilized in dishes like tahini-halva and Shukri-halva, which are vulnerable to contamination by various microorganisms, with conditions conducive to bacterial growth [9].

In recent decades, foods with low water activity and high fat content have been associated with certain outbreaks.

Bacterial foodborne diseases are more prevalent than those caused by other microorganisms. Epidemiological studies indicate that some outbreaks of salmonellosis have occurred through sesame products. For instance, in 2001, 27 Swedish individuals were reported to have ingested *Salmonella enterica* from imported contaminated halva [10, 11]. However, low water activity in tahini prevents *Salmonella* spp. from growing, while the high amount of fat may help them survive for a long time [4, 5]. The survival of foodborne pathogens in low water activity environments has increased due to exposure to various treatments, compared to pathogenic cells that thrive in high water activity conditions [12].

Studies have shown that *Bacillus* spp. could be present in tahini [8, 13], which is the main cause of foodborne intoxication. This form of poisoning can occur even if viable pathogens are not present in the consumed food [14]. Product recalls have been reported after detecting bacilli contamination that might pose a threat to human health. Additionally, since some species of bacilli are spore-forming, they might be of great concern in terms of their ability to survive longer [12]. *Escherichia coli* is another bacterium that can survive in tahini and halva during processing

and storage at various temperatures [15]. It has been reported that the bacterium can survive in tahini and tahini-based products during storage at temperatures ranging from 10°C to 37°C.

The present study assesses the microbiological contamination of sesame products (tahini, tahini-halva, and Shukri-halva) using culturing methods. Samples were collected from Iranian retailers. Given the significance of Iran in exporting these products, such evaluation is highly necessary to prevent foodborne diseases and poisonings.

2. Materials and Methods

Sample collection

Tahini-halva, tahini, and Shukri-halva samples were collected between March 21, 2022, and November 21, 2022. A total of 177 samples (59 tahini-halva, 59 tahini, and 59 Shukri-halva) were obtained from Iranian producers and retailers in the Yazd province from various suppliers. Samples were collected in their original packaging and sterilized carriers, then transported to the laboratory and stored at 4°C.

Microbiological analysis

Detection of *Escherichia coli*

10 grams of homogenized samples were taken and transferred to 90 ml of Ringer's solution. Subsequently, 1 ml of the suspension was aliquoted into a tube containing Lauryl Sulfate Tryptose broth (LST broth) (Merck), along with a Durham tube, and incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours. Following incubation, 0.1 ml of the suspension from the gas-producing tubes was inoculated into *Escherichia coli* (EC) broth (Quelab) with a Durham tube, and incubated at 44°C for 24-48 hours. Subsequent to gas production, 0.1 ml of the samples was transferred to peptone water and incubated at 44°C for 24-48 hours. Confirmation tests were carried out in accordance with the standards set by the Food and Drug Administration of Iran (FDA) (Standard Designation Number 2964), including the indole test.

Detection of *Salmonella* spp.

25 grams of homogenized samples were transferred to 225 ml of peptone water and then incubated at 37°C for 18 hours; this process is referred to as pre-enrichment. Following this, 1 ml of suspension from the pre-enrichment media was transferred to 10 ml of Rappaport Vassiliadis Soy (RVS) broth (Quelab), and gray colonies were observed. These colonies were subsequently transferred to Xylose Lysine Deoxycholate (XLD) agar (Quelab). Blue-green colonies with a black center were selected on Hectone Enteric (HE) Agar (Quelab). Colonies matching the color of the media, which appeared transparent with a black center, were chosen on Xylose Lysine Deoxycholate (XLD) agar (Merck). Colorless and transparent colonies with a black center were selected on *Salmonella Shigella* (SS) Agar, while pink colonies were chosen on Brilliant Green Agar (BG). Confirmation of these colonies was carried out using Triple Sugar Iron (TSI) Agar (Merck), Urine Agar (Merck), Indole Nitrite (Merck), Lysine Decarboxylase (Merck) Agar, and serological tests (FDA Standard Designation Number 1810).

Detection of *Bacillus cereus*

10 grams of homogenized samples were transferred to 90 ml of Ringer's solution, followed by the preparation of serial dilutions. From each concentration obtained through serial dilution, 1 ml was cultured onto Mannitol Egg Yolk Polymyxin (MYP) Agar

(Merck) and then incubated at 30°C for 18-24 hours. Subsequently, the cultures were examined for the presence of large pink colonies with a sedimentary halo, and a certain number of these colonies were selected for confirmatory tests. To confirm the identity of these colonies, they were streaked onto Blood agar (Merck) and incubated for 18 to 24 hours at 30°C. A hemolysis test was then conducted. Confirmation of *Bacillus cereus* presence relied on the formation of pink colonies with a sedimentary halo on MYP agar and a positive hemolysis test, indicated by a completely transparent halo surrounding the colony on Blood agar. (FDA Standard Designation Number 2324).

Statistical analysis

Results were presented as frequency and percentage. Fisher's exact test was used to investigate whether the microbiological contamination is different among main sesame products. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical considerations

This study was approved by the ethics committee of the Iran University of Medical Sciences, Tehran, Iran, with the following code: (IR.IUMS.REC.1400.695).

3. Results

Prevalence of *Salmonella* spp., *E. coli* and *B. cereus*

A total of 177 sesame samples were collected from producers and retailers in the Yazd province of Iran to isolate and identify contamination by *E. coli*, *B. cereus*, and *Salmonella* spp. Contamination with *E. coli*, *B. cereus*, and *Salmonella* spp. was detected in 16 (9%), 17 (9.6%), and 3 (1.7%) samples, respectively. The prevalence of *Salmonella* spp., *E. coli*, and *B. cereus* is summarized in Table 1.

Based on the distribution of samples among different products, 59 samples of tahini, 59 samples of Shukri-halva, and 59 samples of tahini-halva were examined. The findings revealed that 17 samples of Shukri-halva, 3 samples of tahini, and 16 samples of tahini-halva were contaminated. Consequently, out of the 36 positive samples, 33 samples (92%) were contaminated with *E. coli* or *B. cereus*, indicating that sesame products are potentially more susceptible to these contaminations than *Salmonella* spp.

Figure 1 depicts a mosaic plot illustrating the contamination of two pathogens, *E. coli* and *B. cereus*, with associated p-values derived from Fisher's exact test, comparing the proportions of detected positive outcomes across three sesame products. The proportions of detected *E. coli* were similar among the sesame products ($P = 0.135$). However, it is evident that the proportions of detected *B. cereus* contaminations varied across the products ($P = 0.002$). Since the number of positive *Salmonella* samples was consistent across sesame products (one positive sample per product), no significant differences between products in terms of *Salmonella* contamination were anticipated.

Contamination with *E. coli*, *B. cereus*, and *Salmonella* spp. was detected in 16 (9%), 17 (9.6%), and 3 (1.7%) samples, respectively (refer to Table 1). A significant difference was noted among these proportions (Fisher's exact test, $P = 0.002$). Out of the 36 positive samples, 33 (92%) were found to be contaminated with either *E. coli* or *B. cereus*, indicating that sesame products are potentially more susceptible to these contaminations compared to *Salmonella*.

Figure 1. Mosaic plot comparing the distribution of positive samples across three sesame products.

Table 1. Detection of bacteria in tested samples. $P \geq 0.05$ considered not significantly difference.

Bacteria	Number of positive samples			Number of total samples	P value
	Shukri-Halva	Tahini	Tahini-Halva		
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	8	2	6	16 (9%)	
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	8	0	9	17 (9.6%)	0.002
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	1	1	1	3 (1.7%)	

4. Discussion

Sesame is an ancient crop known for its abundant nutritional elements. It is utilized in the production of various foods such as bread, pastries, and tahini. Tahini and halva are derived from sesame through grinding, and they are predominantly used in Middle Eastern and Mediterranean cuisine. Despite its beneficial minerals, fats, and proteins, sesame and its derivatives create a favorable environment for bacterial growth. During production, additional preservation or processing of sesame seeds and products can lead to microbial contamination during distribution. Despite the use of high temperatures and high concentrations of sugar in processing sesame products, contaminations still occur [16].

The source of contamination may vary depending on the processing undergone by the seeds. Inappropriate hygiene practices during packaging or transportation, known as cross-contamination, could be a likely route of contamination. To ensure the quality of sesame products and protect consumers, all actors involved in the production chain should receive training in

hygienic practices, that mitigate such contaminations, Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point (HACCP) and Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP) protocols should be implemented, especially in countries with lower hygiene standards. Additionally, thorough microbiological examinations at various stages of production are necessary in all factories. While some outbreaks linked to sesame or its derivatives have been reported in various countries [10, 17], no such outbreaks have been documented in Iran.

Salmonella is recognized as one of the major pathogenic genera associated with foodborne bacterial outbreaks [10, 18]. The absence of prior heat treatment might be the cause of these contaminations, as adequate heat can effectively mitigate them [19]. Our investigation indicated a contamination rate of 1.7% with *Salmonella* spp., so, Similar to our findings, *Soltan Dallal MM et al.* [20] reported isolating 2% *Salmonella* Group D from tahini-halva in the Yazd province of Iran in 2015. Additionally, a study conducted in Turkey found that 1% of the tahini-halva samples were contaminated with *Salmonella* spp., that 120 tahini-

halva samples were examined. However, research from Germany revealed that 1 (8.33%) sample out of 12 tahini samples was contaminated with *Salmonella* spp. They examined various sesame products imported from different countries, and most of the contaminated products were from a manufacturer in Turkey [21]. While in another study, conducted in Australia reported 31% of *Salmonella* contamination from 91 tahini samples, caused outbreak [17].

Escherichia coli is a significant contributor to global foodborne illnesses, affecting individuals of all ages and demographics. The presence of *E. coli* serves as an indicator of fecal contamination and plays a crucial role in identifying contamination within the food supply chain, spanning from raw material acquisition to the transportation of the final product. Detecting *E. coli* in the tahini-halva samples obtained in our investigation would have signaled contamination during the manufacturing or handling stages before the products were commercially distributed [22].

Our study revealed a 9% contamination rate of *E. coli*. Comparable findings were reported in research conducted in Turkey, where *E. coli* was detectable in 11% of tahini-halva samples, that in this study 120 tahini-halva were examined. In Yazd province of Iran in 2015, *Soltan Dallal MM et al.* [20] reported *E. coli* contamination in tahini at a rate of 8% out of 100 samples. as our study, they utilized FDA standards for their experiment. In another study, the number of *E. coli* colonies was counted using the MPN method, and all samples were found to be less than 3 MPN/g, which was deemed acceptable according to the Turkish Food Codex [22]. In a research study conducted in Turkey in 2022 [23], among 40 tahini- halva samples, no contamination with *E. coli* was found.

Bacillus cereus is ubiquitously present in the environment, and its ability to form resilient spores poses a significant risk to food safety. This bacterium is estimated to contribute to foodborne outbreaks worldwide, accounting for approximately 1.4% to 12% of incidents [24]. Our examination indicated that *B. cereus* accounted for 9.6% of contaminations detected. Additionally, in a study conducted by *Soltan Dallal MM et al.* in Iran [20], *B. cereus* was found in 4% of tahini samples. Also, investigations of food samples in Kenya showed that 47.2% of samples were contaminated with *B. cereus*, a significantly higher rate compared to our findings [25].

Due to the traditional and localized nature of Shukri-halva as a specific Iranian food, comprehensive data for analysis were unavailable.

The differences observed in contamination rates of *E. coli*, *B. cereus*, and *Salmonella* spp. in sesame products across different studies may stem from various factors, including geographical variations and varying levels of hygiene in different regions. Geographical factors such as climate, soil composition, and environmental conditions can influence the prevalence of these bacteria in food samples. Additionally, differences in agricultural practices and food handling techniques between regions may contribute to varying contamination rates. Socioeconomic factors, including access to clean water, sanitation facilities, and education about food safety practices, also play a crucial role in determining overall hygiene levels. Furthermore, variation in regulatory standards and enforcement of food safety regulations across regions may lead to disparities in contamination rates. Cultural practices and dietary habits unique to each region could further affect the likelihood of food contamination with these bacteria.

5. Conclusion

Given Iran's significant role in exporting sesame products, vigilant monitoring and detection of contaminants are crucial to mitigate the risk of foodborne infections and illnesses. This study's findings unveiled differing levels of contamination by *Salmonella* spp., *E. coli*, and *B. cereus* in sesame products, with tahini-halva displaying the highest contamination levels, while tahini exhibited comparatively lower levels. However, it's important to acknowledge the limitations inherent in our study. Therefore, the utilization of molecular-based techniques and precise bacterial quantification methods is recommended to enhance the accuracy and comprehensiveness of future investigations in this field.

Authors Contributions

Niloufar Rashidi designed the study, Najmeh Zareii conducted the experimental works, Niloufar Rashidi & Alireza Mortazavighahi analyzed the data, Alireza Mortazavighahi & Javad Allahverdy wrote the manuscript, Niloufar Rashidi & Alireza Mortazavighahi revised the manuscript.

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